

THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATION IN THE CONVENTION ON THE RIGHTS OF THE CHILD

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Abstract. *This study provides information on educational reforms and the protection of children's rights as outlined in the Convention on the Rights of the Child. It also provides information on the opportunities created in education and the broad development of the education sector in this Convention.*

Keywords: *Education, children's rights, Convention on the Rights of the Child, upbringing, opportunities in education.*

BOLA HUQUQLARI HAQIDAGI KONVENSIYADA TA'LIMNING AHAMIYATI

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotda bola huquqlari to'g'risidagi konvensiyada keltirib o'tilgan ta'lim reformalari va bolalar huquqlarini himoya qilish haqidagi ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan.*

Shuningdek, mazkur konvensiyada ta'limda yaratilgan imkoniyatlar va ta'lim sohasini keng turda rivojlantirish bo'yicha ma'lumotlar asoslab beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Ta'lim, bola huquqlari, bola huquqlari to'g'risidagi konvensiya, tarbiya, ta'limda imkoniyatlar.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В КОНВЕНЦИИ О ПРАВАХ РЕБЕНКА

Аннотация. *В этом исследовании представлена информация об образовательных реформах и защите прав детей, как указано в Конвенции о правах ребенка. В нем также представлена информация о возможностях, созданных в образовании, и широком развитии сектора образования в этой Конвенции.*

Ключевые слова: *Образование, права детей, Конвенция о правах ребенка, воспитание, возможности в образовании.*

Introduction

Today, a lot of practical work is being carried out in our country to protect children in educational, social, economic, legal, and spiritual aspects.

An appropriate legal framework has been formed in this regard. In particular, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Family Code, the Civil Code, the Labor Code, the Criminal Code, and a number of other legislative acts reflect the norms of protecting children's rights. The Convention on the Rights of the Child is one of the most important documents in the field of human rights. Currently, the protection of children and ensuring the full implementation of their rights has become the obligation of states around the world. The Convention on the Rights of the Child can serve as a full basis for this. Since that day, guarantees for the protection of children's rights have been provided all over the world and an international mechanism for their protection has been created. The Convention is, without exaggeration, the first international legal instrument strengthening the guarantees for the protection of children's rights, and the participating states are obliged to strictly comply with its provisions. The Convention sets common standards that reflect the cultural, economic, social and political aspects of individual countries. Each state has the right and opportunity to implement these standards, taking into account its national characteristics. Previously, care for a child was carried out only in cases of need for protection. In connection with the adoption of the Convention, a completely new concept was established. It emphasized that care and protection are not a matter of privilege, but a right.

With the entry into force of the Convention, it became a set of strictly defined basic social and legal criteria, procedures and rules for children. The Convention initially clarified the concept of a child, expanded the scope of the rights and freedoms of the child, the document provides for the legal protection of children who are victims of cruel torture and armed conflicts, as well as children who have violated the law and are incompetent. It also addresses the issues of protecting children from certain negative phenomena, for example, from the consequences of violence. Since the first years of independence, our country has been paying serious attention to the consistent reform of the system of protecting children's rights, the introduction of international standards in this regard into national legislation, and the improvement of legislation. To date, our country has acceded to all major international instruments on the protection of the interests and rights of children. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child" has determined the main directions of state policy on the protection of children's rights. This law serves to ensure the rights and freedoms of every child living in our country, protect his life and health, prevent discrimination, protect his honor and dignity, and ensure equality of rights and opportunities. This law clearly defines the guarantees of the child's rights to life, personal integrity, family environment, property ownership, work, education and meaningful leisure, and social protection.

After all, civil society can be a powerful force in the upbringing, protection, and participation of children in society, as well as the quality of social security services. Article 28 of the Convention on the Rights of the Child states the following: States Parties recognize the right of the child to education and, with a view to achieving this right progressively on the basis of equal opportunity, shall, in particular: (a) Make primary education free and compulsory; (b) Encourage the development of various forms of secondary education, both general and vocational, and shall make such education accessible to all children and shall take appropriate measures, including the introduction of free education and, in case of need, financial assistance; (c) Ensure, by all appropriate means, the access of every child to higher education on the basis of his or her ability; (d) Ensure that all children have access to information and materials in the field of education and vocational training; (e) Promote regular school attendance and reduce the number of school dropouts. States Parties shall take all appropriate measures to ensure that school discipline is administered in a manner that reflects respect for the child's human dignity and is in accordance with the present Convention. States Parties shall encourage and develop international cooperation in matters relating to education, in particular in order to contribute to the eradication of ignorance and illiteracy throughout the world and to facilitate the use of scientific and technical knowledge and modern teaching methods. In this regard, special attention shall be paid to the needs of developing countries. In this regard, in order to further enhance the legal culture of children and increase the legal knowledge of the population regarding the rights of the child, it is appropriate to pay greater attention to the following: firstly, to strengthen the theoretical aspects of education and upbringing in relation to the rights of the child, as well as to further increase its practical effectiveness; secondly, to ensure that organizations implementing education and upbringing of children pay greater attention in their curricula to international norms on the rights of the child to which the Republic of Uzbekistan has acceded, to universal human values, to advanced foreign experience and, of course, to national traditions and values historically formed in the country; thirdly, to increase the effectiveness of the use of modern information and pedagogical technologies in teaching children's rights; fourthly, to further strengthen research on children's rights, especially scientific and sociological research aimed at studying their own and the population's legal culture on children's rights; fifthly, it is emphasized to achieve mutual understanding and cooperation between educational organizations and state bodies, civil society institutions, in particular neighborhoods, on children's rights. It is important to strengthen the role of the education system and sports in the formation of a healthy child, expand the network of preschool educational institutions, provide them with highly qualified and experienced

pedagogical personnel, radically increase the level of children's preparation for school in ensuring the high quality of primary education, widely introduce advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies into practice, widely promote a healthy lifestyle, especially among girls, and implement specific measures for physical education. Preschool education is aimed at forming a healthy and mature personality of a child preparing for school. This education is carried out in the family, in kindergartens and in other educational organizations, regardless of their form of ownership, from six to seven years old. Information is provided on the basic principles of the "Convention on the Rights of the Child". The Convention on the Rights of the Child is the only international document that sets out criteria for the well-being of children at different stages of development, as well as a formal legal framework that strictly stipulates that participating states must implement its provisions. Although the Convention establishes general standards, it reflects the cultural, economic, social and political aspects of individual states. Each state has the right and opportunity to take into account its own national characteristics in the implementation of these standards.

Conclusion

To date, all conditions have been created in our country for children to receive free and quality education. It is also stated in the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the protection of children's rights and supervision of the upbringing of minors who have strayed into the path of crime. We must encourage young people to properly use the opportunities created in our country, and educate them in the spirit of loyalty to the homeland.

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